

Recycling of glass fibre thermoset composites by cold incorporation into a sustainable inorganic polymer matrix

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MATERIALS ENGINEERING

Current issue: Recycling challenges

◆ Large volume

Table1: Dismantled wind turbines in Belgium (since 1987)

Dismantle reason	Percentage	Service years
Blade failure	3.2%	8
Decommissioned	25.8%	20
Repower	67.7%	16
Not recorded	3.2%	8

Repower: replacing old WT with newer and more efficient models
Data source: Windpower (updated to 6th June 2023)

Belgium dismantled WT shows an average lifetime of 17 years, shorten than typical design lifetime of 20-30 years

Estimated EoL blade waste: case of Belgium

Current issue: Recycling challenges

◆ Cost-effectiveness

Current issue: Recycling challenges

◆ Mechanical recycling barriers

Cons (vs virgin GF):

- × Shorter length
- × Lower quality
- × Increased variations
- × Hindered bonding with new polymer
- × **Low added-value**

Ground GFRP material

a few microns to 10mm

Hammer milling
(or other high-speed grinding)

Fine GFRP recycle

100 microns

Virgin GF (1-3€/kg)

Filler (0.25€/kg)

Recycling GFRP composites: A double waste solution

A double waste solution: Cement alternative – 1, Inorganic polymer

Copper scrap

Copper

By-product

Worldwide: 50 MT/year
In Flanders: 376 kT/year, 8.5% of cement consumption

Non-ferrous metallurgical slag

Alkaline Activators

$\text{FeO}_x\text{-CaO-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiO}_2$
Geopolymerization

Brittle:

compressive strength-20~50MPa

flexural strength-3~5MPa

Inorganic polymer (IP)

Pros (vs cement):

- ✓ 10-30% Cheaper
- ✓ Less 17-47% CO_2
- ✓ Fire resistant
- ✓ Acid resistant

The synthetic IP lacks sufficient tensile strength and needs reinforcements for structural use

A double waste solution: reinforcements alternatives – 2,rGFP

Typical virgin GF-reinforcement products:

Ground GF
(0.25€/kg)

Chopped GF stands
(~1€/kg)

Chopped long GF stands
(1-2€/kg)

GFRP rebar
(~5.42€/kg)

Recovered GFRP (rGFP):

Valorization key: maximizing the length and integrity of rGFP

Recycling GFRP composites: Goals and targets

1-Develop a mechanical recycling route

- for longer and higher-integrity rGFP

2-Effectiveness-cost Investigation:

- 1-Assess the weight fractions of rGFP
- 2-Compare the performance of rGFP vs. vGF
- 3-Evaluate the environment impact
- 4-Assess the economic viability

1-Develop a mechanical recycling route

Blade pieces (length~6-12m, thickness~80mm):
brittle and abrasive
medium-hard to hard comminution

(Waterjet) & (shear and roller mill)

Shredder classification based on the size and hardness of feed material

1-Develop a mechanical recycling route

Process1:mainly waterjet

Process2:mainly shear& roller mill

2-Effectiveness Investigation: 1-rGFP properties

	rGFP mixture	Virgin Chopped GF
rGFP-rebar	Can be several meters long	Length range: 6-38mm
rGFP-1 Bundle	Avg=32mm Max=80mm 1.47g/cm ³	
rGFP-2 Fibrous	Avg=7mm Max=56mm 1.38g/cm ³	
rGFP-3 Fine	Avg=0.7mm Max=1.4mm 1.62g/cm ³	

2-Effectiveness Investigation: 2-rGFP v.s. virgin GF

Two benchmarks to consider the size effect

Beam weights for equivalent deflections	
<i>Beam (loaded in bending)</i> ——strength limited design	
<i>Function and constraints</i>	Material indices
<i>Shape and length specified; section area free</i>	$\frac{\rho}{\sigma_f^{2/3}}$
ρ -Composite's bulk density σ_f -Flexural strength	

Reference 1:
Glass fibre-concrete premix(GFRC)
(ACI-549.3-22)

Reference 2:
Virgin GFRP rebar-inorganic polymer concrete
(GFPrb-IPC) (ACI-440.1R-15)

Performance data obtained from experiments and ACI report (ACI-549.3-22)

For example:

Material a: rGFP-IP

Material b: vGF-cement

Substitute factor (a measure to reference) :

$$\lambda = \text{Mass}(a) / \text{mass}(b) = \rho_a / \rho_b * (\sigma_{fb} / \sigma_{fa})^{2/3}$$

	GFRC ¹	rGFP1-IP	rGFP2-IP	rGFP3-IP	GFPrb-IPC ²	rGFPPrb-IPC
Properties*						
ρ	2.06	2.50	2.50	2.55	2.54	2.54
σ_f	10	26.70	17.20	10.10	24.16	23.4
Substitute factor λ	<i>The performance of rGRP-IP/IPC in relation to the reference material</i>					
	1	1.58	1.18	0.81	1	0.98
Substitute factor λ'	<i>1 kg of rGFR in IP composite can substitute xkg VGF/GFPrb</i>					
	-	1.25	0.93	0.64	-	0.98

2-Effectiveness Investigation: 3-Environmental impact

◆ Life cycle analysis (LCA)

- ◆ Functional unit: 1 ton of waste GFRP entered in the treatment routes
- ◆ Database: Ecoinvent3.5 and literature reference
- ◆ Impact method: EF v2.0
- ◆ Analyzed impact: Global warming potential (GWP)
- ◆ Versus conventional waste treatment methods:
 - Landfill
 - Incineration with energy recovery
 - Co-processing in cement-kiln

System boundary for the proposed mechanical route

2-Cost Investigation: 4-Cost

◆ Life cycle cost analysis (LCC) :

Evaluates GFRP waste disposal routes from two perspectives of key stakeholders

- ◆ 1-Waste owner: Average cost per mass unit of waste (C_w)
 - The gate fee to be paid to the government or industry for waste disposal
- ◆ 2-Recycling plant: Average cost per mass unit of recovered rebar (C_r)
 - The lowest selling price of rGFRP rebar for the recycling plant

$$C_w = \frac{REV(at\ NPV=0)}{Waste\ input\ capacity} \quad (1) \quad C_r = \frac{REV(at\ NPV=0) - \sum Revenue\ of\ by-products(rGFP\ mixture)}{Recovered\ rebar\ capacity} \quad (2)$$

$$(Net\ present\ value)\ NPV = -INV + \sum_{t=1}^{10} \frac{(REV-TC) \times (1-a) + D}{(1+r)^t} \quad (3)$$

Investment (INV): 160 000 € of capacity less than 100t_GFRP waste/year
220 000 € of capacity of 900t_GFRP waste/year

Assume: The operating time of recycling plant (10 years)

a-tax rate=25%

r-internal rate of return=10%

REV: Annual Revenue of process

D:Depreciation ($D=INV/H$)

TC: Total annual cost ($TC=D+ Cost(raw\ material, utility, labour\ and\ maintenance)$)

Environmental impact-GWP

For 75mm-GFRP, increasing waterjet speed from 0.1m/min to 0.3m/min at pilot scale, to 0.6m/min at industry level

Cost

Key takeaway

Technical feasibility

- recovers concentrated long reinforcements (90wt% of rebar)
- no need to separate the resin residues

Environmental benefit & Cost-effectiveness

- If waterjet cutting speed is increased to 0.6m/min (for 75mm GFRP)

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Abstract submission deadline 31 Mar 2024

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